

Research paper

Prognostic of lithium-ion batteries using a combination of physical modeling and hybrid multi-layer perceptron particle filter[☆]

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ABSTRACT

With the European Union legislative push to phase out internal combustion engines by 2035, the demand for electric vehicles and efficient energy storage solutions, particularly lithium-ion batteries, is set to rise. Addressing this demand necessitates both the optimization of battery lifespan and the development of robust methodologies for real-time assessment of state of health and prediction of remaining useful life. This study introduces a novel hybrid grey-box prognostic and health management framework that combines a physical battery model with a multi-layer perceptron particle filter (MLP-PF) for real-time estimation of degradation parameters. The approach leverages an electrochemical model developed in Modelica to simulate battery voltage and track degradation parameters, thereby capturing the battery dynamic behavior over time. By integrating a data-driven MLP-PF, this method adapts the physical degradation parameters, ensuring ongoing and precise estimation of remaining useful life. Experimental validation, in terms of accuracy and confidence interval coverage, confirms the framework capability in prediction and relative quantification of uncertainties. These results underscore the framework practical utility for battery management systems in electric vehicles, providing an adaptable and accurate tool for decision-makers in battery maintenance and replacement.

1. Introduction

In the past decade, electric vehicles (EVs) have steadily gained market share, with their numbers tripling in just the last three years (IEA, 2022). This surge in popularity can be attributed to several factors: (i) a constantly expanding variety of EV models, with over 500 types available in 2022 (IEA, 2023), (ii) robust political support in the form of incentives and subsidies aimed at phasing out internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles (for instance, the European Union approved legislation limiting the use of ICE to e-fuels starting from 2035, to combat air pollution and address climate change) and (iii) advancements in battery technology (Mahmud et al., 2022), resulting in more efficient batteries that offer comparable driving ranges to traditional ICE vehicles.

EVs power source are the lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), which offer higher power-to-weight ratio and better rechargeable properties when compared to other battery typologies (Chen et al., 2019). Moreover, declining LIBs prices in recent years have made EVs more affordable, further contributing to their development. The landscape slightly shifted

in 2022 when battery pack prices increased for the first time since 2010 due to supply chain shortages and rising metal costs (BloombergNEF, 2022). Despite this, the demand for LIBs is predicted to surge in all regions: China remains the dominant manufacturer, but an increasing number of projects are underway in Europe and the United States to reduce dependence by constructing lithium-ion battery gigafactories, with an expected total production capacity of around 900 GWh by 2030 (Heiner, 2022).

In this context, the research into novel and efficient methods for optimizing battery usage is of paramount importance. The implementation of effective maintenance strategies can extend battery lifespan, reducing its operating costs. LIB performance deteriorates with usage and aging, eventually resulting in an inability to meet the required power demands. Consequently, battery replacement becomes necessary to maintain optimal vehicle performance. The incorrect use can result in sudden failures and even thermal runaways, posing serious safety risks, including potential vehicle fires (Sun et al., 2020). The limited safety performances are currently the main drawback of LIBs, limiting

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their further expansion and jeopardizing their reputation (Chen et al., 2021).

To address this challenge, EVs incorporate a battery management system (BMS), tasked with monitoring and regulating battery parameters to ensure safe and efficient operation (Li et al., 2020). Data collected by battery sensors present opportunities for developing diagnostic and prognostic strategies aimed at enhancing safety, optimizing performance, and extending battery lifespan. Consequently, smarter approaches for battery recharge, replacement, and maintenance can be derived, as demonstrated in Dickerson et al. (2015).

Considering the strategic significance of these challenges, numerous studies in the literature have focused on the prognosis and diagnosis of LIBs in literature. Prognostic and health management (PHM) is an engineering discipline aimed to use physical knowledge, information and data of complex systems to detecting anomalies, estimate their state of health (SOH) and predicting their remaining useful life (RUL) (Zio, 2022). The intricate electrochemical processes happening inside batteries cause complicated, non-linear degradation behaviors, making these tasks very challenging. Hu et al. (2020) provides an overview of the methods for the PHM of batteries, clustered in model-based, data-driven and hybrid methods. In model-based approaches, battery degradation processes are described through physical modeling to depict its trajectory, whereas data-driven methods utilize statistical or machine learning techniques as surrogate of the physical model.

Model-based approaches can range from relatively simple equivalent circuit models (Zou et al., 2015) to more intricate complete electrochemical models (Lyu et al., 2017), enabling focused study of specific phenomena, such as a thermal runaway (Tran et al., 2022). Yet, escalating model complexity inevitably extends computational time, frequently conflicting with the real-time demands of the application.

Data-driven methods leverage historical monitoring data to construct a surrogate model of battery behavior, enabling predictions of its performance, SOH and eventually remaining useful life (RUL) (Ren and Du, 2023). These methods prioritize degradation trend analysis while disregarding underlying physical and internal mechanisms. With the widespread interest in machine learning, particularly artificial neural networks (ANN), many recent studies have advocated for this approach (Zheng et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2018; Khaleghi et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021). While such methods often offer acceptable prediction accuracy and computational efficiency, concerns persist regarding their lack of interpretability and the availability of sufficient historical data for specific applications.

Many hybrid approaches have been proposed to overcome the limitations of both model-based methods (which are computationally intensive and require expert knowledge) and data-driven methods (which lack interpretability and necessitate substantial data). Among these, physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) enable the inclusion of partial differential equations in the neural network training process. For example, Li et al. (2021) focused on estimating batteries' internal hidden states by combining an electrochemical-thermal model with a deep neural network, while (Shi et al., 2022) combined a long-short term memory (LSTM) network with physics equations. Additionally, Nascimento et al. (2021) integrated an electrochemical model with a deep neural network to improve alignment with experimental data and quantify uncertainty. More recently, Wang et al. (2023a) developed a robust singular filtering-Gaussian process regression-long short-term memory (SF-GPR-LSTM) model for lithium-ion batteries, enhancing estimation accuracy and adaptability to fast aging and variable currents. Wang et al. (2023b) also proposed an anti-noise adaptive long short-term memory neural network (ANA-LSTM) that leverages a dual closed-loop observation approach and multi-feature collaboration to improve the robustness and precision of battery remaining useful life predictions under complex operating conditions. Reza et al. (2024) offers a comprehensive and recent overview of advancements in RUL prediction for lithium-ion batteries, emphasizing the need for a deeper

understanding of underlying conditions through physics-based techniques and particularly advocating for hybrid methods to mitigate the limitations of individual models.

The persistent challenge of managing the intricate electrochemical processes within batteries still remains a critical concern, since varying external conditions and the different usage patterns lead similar batteries to degrade very differently from one another, posing a considerable hurdle. To account for this, Cadini et al. (2019) proposed an adaptable methodology called multi-layer perceptron particle filter (MLP-PF): the capacity measurements of a battery are used in real-time to predict the battery remaining useful life, while adapting to changes in external conditions and to unexpected anomalies occurring during its lifetime. Yet, relying on capacity measurements for real-time predictions presents a significant obstacle: obtaining precise capacity data in real-time is not feasible. Consequently, it relies on the precise knowledge of the battery SOH to estimate the remaining available energy. However, a reliable estimation of the SOH is also a difficult task and, for example in the maritime industry, it requires an annual in-situ capacity testing (Vanem et al., 2023), which is both time consuming and expensive.

This work addresses two key challenges: (i) developing an adaptable methodology to capture changes in degradation trajectories, and (ii) enabling online application using real-time data directly from the BMS. The proposed approach combines an electrochemical physics-based battery model with real-time estimation of degradation parameters through a data-driven framework, creating a grey-box methodology. By monitoring physical degradation parameters, the physics-based model provides insight into battery internal processes, while the MLP-PF enhances prognostic accuracy and adaptability. This novel framework processes raw voltage data from the BMS to deliver real-time battery state of health insights and performance predictions, empowering decision-makers to make informed choices about battery usage and maintenance.

This paper is organized as follows: the proposed PHM framework is presented in Section 2. Section 3 describes the physical model and Section 4 presents the optimization process of the degradation parameters. In Section 5, the concept of the MLP-PF is introduced, while the results obtained with the proposed approach are detailed in Section 6. Lastly, Section 7 presents conclusions drawn from this work and outlines future developments.

2. PHM framework

Prognostic and health management is an essential field in the realm of asset management and maintenance, particularly when it comes to systems that rely on critical components like batteries. The primary objectives of PHM are to anticipate failures, monitor the state of health, and predict the remaining useful life of these assets. This proactive approach to maintenance has become increasingly critical in optimizing the performance, reliability, and safety of various systems. In the context of batteries, PHM can have a profound impact on decision-making for both private users and fleet managers. To achieve these objectives effectively, it is crucial to derive indicators that are easily understandable, even for non-technical individuals. Whether it is a private vehicle owner or a fleet manager, decision-makers need clear and actionable information. Complicated technical data or complex models can be overwhelming and challenging to interpret. Hence, the development of user-friendly indicators is a key focus of PHM systems, ensuring that the insights they provide are accessible and actionable by all stakeholders.

For this purpose, this paper proposes a framework composed of three main areas: calibration, propagation and prognostic (Fig. 1).

The first, calibration (orange left section in Fig. 1), is needed to constantly calibrate the physical model. The battery electrochemical degradation model has been developed based on Daigle and Kulkarni (2013) by means of Modelica language (OpenModelica), and the degradation is modeled by 3 parameter: maximum number of lithium-ions

Fig. 1. Proposed PHM framework for estimating the battery RUL and evaluating its performance.

available q_{\max} , internal resistance R_0 and diffusion coefficient D . The 3 parameters evolves over time due to the electrochemical reactions happening inside the battery, resulting in a permanent loss of capacity. The model, based on physical equation and initialized with the starting parameters q_0 , R_0 and D_0 , is compared with the voltage real-time data (the measurements) coming from the BMS. By use of the optimization algorithm COBYLA (Powell, 1994) it is possible to infer the optimal hidden degradation parameters which minimize the error between the measured voltage data and the model output. This operation occurs at each cycle, when a new measurement is available from the BMS. This is necessary because batteries can vary significantly in behavior due to external conditions, usage patterns, and even internal defects. The calibration phase ensures that the model accurately represents the unique characteristics of the specific battery in use. This real-time calibration is a crucial foundation for accurate prognostic insights.

Once the parameters have been calibrated, the next phase involves their propagation (blue central section in Fig. 1). The historical data of known batteries are combined with the newly identified hidden parameters, a task executed by the MLP-PF. The goal of the MLP-PF is to derive the probability density functions (PDFs) of the degradation parameters in each future instants of time, in a Bayesian perspective: a multi-layer perceptron neural network is trained on the degradation historical data, constituting the prior knowledge; each time a new observation is available, the PF update the MLP parameters, obtaining the posterior PDF, hence adapting to the specific battery. This phase extends the understanding of how these parameters change over time, enabling the prediction of the future battery behavior with their uncertainty.

The prognostic phase (green right section in Fig. 1) utilizes the information generated in the previous phases to provide actionable insights. The PDFs of each parameters derived from the MLP-PF are used to determine the RUL of the battery, which is defined as the remaining number of cycles during which the battery can reliably provide a certain power output. Finally, a Monte Carlo approach simulates the battery future performance, exploiting the physical model with the propagated parameters, giving precious indication on when it is the right time to repair or replace the battery.

In summary, the framework depicted in Fig. 1 is designed to process real-time battery data alongside historical records, translating these datasets into easily interpretable indicators for decision-makers. To gain a comprehensive understanding of this framework intricacies, we will now proceed to explore its core components in greater details. Subsequent sections will delve into the specifics of the underlying physical model, the methodology for parameters propagation, and the other essential elements that collectively render this approach an invaluable tool for enhancing battery performance and reliability.

3. Physical model

A model serves as a mathematical representation of a system, designed to replicate its functionality within a digital framework. This involves employing a set of equations, which can be solved in various ways. To avoid the computational burden of methods such as finite elements, 0D/1D models are often used to describe systems through ordinary differential equations. Modelica is a programming language well suited for designing 0D/1D models (Girard et al., 2015). Within a Modelica framework, the model takes the form of a system of differential equations, solved by dedicated multipurpose third-party tools such as OpenModelica (OpenModelica).

For the calibration of model parameters and to enable interaction between the model and other programming languages better suited for statistical analysis or uncertainty quantification, the functional mock-up interface (FMI) standard (Modelica Association) has been introduced. This standard enables the treatment of the numerical model as a black box within other language frameworks. It consists of an XML file that describes the model variables and a set of possible compiled functions for conducting the simulations. Treating it as a black box, it allows using the functional mock-up unit (FMU) as a callable entity, defining inputs, and obtaining the results of the simulation as outputs.

Thanks to PyFMI (PyFMI) it is feasible to include the FMU in a python script, simplifying the statistical analysis as well as the tuning of the parameters to optimize the numerical model. An example of the optimization and tuning of the parameters will be presented in Section 4.

3.1. Lithium-ion batteries

Lithium-ion batteries are electrochemical devices designed to store and release energy as needed. They offer several key advantages over other types of electrochemical converters. These advantages include their rechargeable nature, lack of memory effect, higher energy density, and longer life cycle. LIBs are typically composed of multiple individual cells, which allow them to be configured in various arrangements to suit the specific requirements of the application at hand. By connecting cells in series or parallel within a battery pack, it is possible to achieve the desired voltage or current levels for a particular application. One of the most commonly used cell formats is the 18650 cell, which is cylindrical and measures 18 millimeters in diameter and 65 millimeters in length. These cells typically have a nominal voltage of 3.7 V and a maximum voltage of 4.2 V. For the purpose of this work, the 18650 cell format with its specific characteristics will be the primary focus. A schematic representation of a LIB structure can be observed in Fig. 2. During the discharge process, mobile ions reside in the negative electrode. When a load is applied, a current is permitted to flow from the positive to the

Fig. 2. Overview of the schematic structure of a lithium-ion battery (Cipolla, 2017).

negative electrode resulting in the release of lithium ions and electrons, which move towards the positive electrode through the separator.

The battery performance degradation is a natural consequence of usage. The two main factors that contribute to the degradation of the battery performances are the loss of active ions and an increase in the internal battery resistance. These degradation processes are influenced by various phenomena, including:

1. Solid electrolyte interface (SEI) growth: formation of a solid layer on the surface of active material. This process can occur both during cycling (charge and discharge) as well as during storage at high temperatures.
2. Lithium corrosion: lithium corrosion involves the gradual degradation of lithium within the battery. This phenomenon results in an irreversible loss of mobile ions.

It is important to note that these degradation processes are not localized and are profoundly affected by external conditions, including temperature and usage patterns. As a result, understanding and predicting the degradation of these devices can be a complex challenge. Additionally, certain phenomena, such as the capacity recovery (Eddahech et al., 2013), can allow the battery to regain some of the lost capacity, further increasing the difficulties in understanding the overall processes occurring within the batteries.

3.2. Battery model

The battery has been modeled by the use of the Modelica language. The final goal of this model is to simulate the output voltage and temperature of the cell battery, in order to compute its state of charge (SOC). The cut-off voltage of the battery, meaning the one defining the end of discharge (EOD) has been defined at 2.5 V. The overall battery voltage V is obtained by the difference between the potential at the positive current collector and the negative current collector, minus the voltage drops caused by solid-phase ohmic resistance V_0 and the surface overpotential V_η .

The maximum available number of ions is defined as

$$q_{\max} = q_p + q_n \quad (1)$$

where q_p and q_n represent the number of ions at the positive and negative electrodes. The mole fraction x_i , where i can be n (negative) or p (positive), is hence defined as:

$$x_i = \frac{q_i}{q_{\max}} \quad (2)$$

and the SOC of the battery is:

$$\text{SOC} = \frac{q_n}{0.6q_{\max}} \quad (3)$$

Table 1

Battery model parameters (Daigle and Kulkarni, 2013).

Parameter	Value
$U_{0,p}$	4.03 V
$A_{p,0}$	-33642.23 J/mol
$A_{p,1}$	0.11 J/mol
$A_{p,2}$	23506.89 J/mol
$A_{p,3}$	-74679.26 J/mol
$A_{p,4}$	14359.34 J/mol
$A_{p,5}$	307849.79 J/mol
$A_{p,6}$	85053.13 J/mol
$A_{p,7}$	-1075148.06 J/mol
$A_{p,8}$	2173.62 J/mol
$A_{p,9}$	991586.68 J/mol
$A_{p,10}$	283423.47 J/mol
$A_{p,11}$	-163020.34 J/mol
$A_{p,12}$	-470297.35 J/mol
$U_{0,n}$	0.01 V
$A_{n,0}$	86.19 J/mol

The battery is considered fully charged when $x_p = 0.4$. Considering Eq. (1), it follows that $x_n + x_p = 1$, from which the factor $\frac{1}{0.6}$ of Eq. (3). On the other side, when the battery is fully discharged, $x_n = 0$ and SOC = 0.

The main equations used to compute the temperature and the output voltage of the battery will now be reported. The interested reader can find a detailed description of these equations in Daigle and Kulkarni (2013).

The potential equilibrium of an electrode is described by the Nernst equation:

$$V_{U,i} = U_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{1 - x_i}{x_i} \right) + V_{\text{INT},i} \quad (4)$$

where U_0 is a reference potential, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature of the battery, F is the Faraday constant, and $V_{\text{INT},i}$ the activity correction term. n indicates the number of electrons transferred in the reaction, equal to 1 in the case of lithium ion. During discharge, x_p grows from 0.4 to 1, while x_n decreases from 0.6 to 0. This results in the decrease of $V_{U,p} - V_{U,n}$.

The two activity coefficients $V_{\text{INT},i}$, where again i can be $p =$ positive or $n =$ negative, are related to the Gibbs excess free energy, computed by Redlich–Kister expansion:

$$V_{\text{INT},i} = \frac{1}{nF} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{N_i} A_{i,k} \left((2x_i - 1)^{k+1} - \frac{2x_i k (1 - x_i)}{(2x_i - 1)^{1-k}} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

where N_i represent the summation indexes for the positive and negative equation, and are $N_p = 12$ and $N_n = 0$. The corresponding $A_{i,k}$ parameters are listed in Table 1.

The variation of the mole fractions x_i , which determine the variation of the voltages, can be derived by the following differential equation, describing how the charge moves through the electrodes. Electrodes are also divided into two volumes, bulk (subscript b) and surface (subscript s). This difference is important because in the electrode the reaction takes place at the surface, causing a concentration gradient between bulk and surface. The diffusion rate from bulk to the surface $\dot{q}_{bs,i}$ can hence be described as:

$$\dot{q}_{bs,i} = \frac{1}{D} (c_{b,i} - c_{s,i}) \quad (6)$$

where D is the diffusion constant and c are the concentrations of lithium ions at the bulk and surface of the two electrodes. The charge q variations can hence be described as:

$$\dot{q}_{s,p} = i_{\text{app}} + \dot{q}_{bs,p} \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{q}_{b,i} = -\dot{q}_{bs,i} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{q}_{s,n} = -i_{\text{app}} + \dot{q}_{bs,n} \quad (9)$$

i_{app} is the applied current. With these equations we can compute $x_{s,i}$ and $x_{b,i}$, and substitute the mole fraction at the surface $x_{s,i}$ in Eq. (4) in place of the total mole fraction. In this way, it is possible to explicitly account for the concentration overpotential at the surface layers, since the observed voltage is only dependent on surface behavior. At the end of the discharge process, the difference between bulk and surface potentials causes a redistribution of ions in the electrodes, resulting in a raise of the voltage, which can be appreciated in Fig. 3.

The output voltage drops further due to the ohmic overpotential V_0 and the surface overpotential $V_{\eta,i}$, respectively defined as:

$$V_0 = i_{app} R_0 \quad (10)$$

$$V_{\eta,i} = \frac{RT}{F\alpha} \operatorname{arcsinh} \left(\frac{J_i}{2J_{i0}} \right) \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) is the Butler-Volmer equation, simplified since α , the symmetry factor is 0.5 for lithium ion while J_i and J_{i0} are the current density and the exchange current density, defined as:

$$J_i = i/S_i \quad (12)$$

$$J_{i0} = k_i(1 - x_{s,i})^\alpha (x_{s,i})^{1-\alpha} \quad (13)$$

where k_i is a lumped parameter. Since the voltage drops take place at the surface level, the exchange current density is computed using $x_{s,i}$.

Voltage drops in the battery do not happen instantaneously. Hence to take that into account we consider:

$$\dot{V}'_0 = (V_0 - V'_0)/\tau_0 \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{V}'_{\eta,i} = (V_{\eta,i} - V'_{\eta,i})/\tau_{\eta,i} \quad (15)$$

The temperature variation of the battery can be computed as:

$$\dot{T} = \frac{(V'_0 + V'_{\eta,p} + V'_{\eta,n})i_{app}}{m_c} + \frac{T_0 - T}{\tau_T} \quad (16)$$

Parameters τ are empirical time constants to account for the transients. Having defined all the components, it is finally possible to define the output battery voltage as:

$$V = V_{U,p} - V_{U,n} - V'_0 - V'_{\eta,p} - V'_{\eta,n} \quad (17)$$

In Fig. 5, two model outputs (dotted lines) are plotted under a constant load of 2 A. The initial output voltage is 4.2 V, corresponding to a SOC of 100%. The process continues until the voltage drops below 2.5 V. At this juncture, the load is reduced to zero, and the voltage stabilizes at the equilibrium voltage. This behavior illustrates the discharge process of the battery under a constant load, and it showcases how the voltage evolves over time as the battery SOC depletes.

In this work, the model is utilized and optimized to simulate commercially available Li-Ion 18650 batteries, whose data are available in the NASA dataset repository. However, the model can be easily adapted to different battery chemistries by adjusting the parameter values in Table 1. Although not demonstrated in this work, the model is not limited to constant current; it can also simulate variable loads, as shown in Daigle and Kulkarni (2015).

3.3. Degradation parameters

As previously discussed in Section 3.1, the performance of a battery gradually deteriorates over time. An illustrative example of this degradation process can be observed in Fig. 3, which represents real-life data from a cell subjected to degradation effects. This degradation has several notable effects on the battery performance, including a reduction in the cell operating time, a general decrease in the overall voltage during usage, and an increase in the equilibrium potential after the cut-off voltage is reached.

To simulate these degradation effects in our model, we consider three key degradation parameters:

Fig. 3. Evolution of the voltage response of battery B0005 subjected to a constant load of 2 A throughout its lifetime. The thickness of each line represents the battery SOH, with thicker lines indicating a healthier state and thinner lines corresponding to more advanced battery degradation. Saha and Goebel (2007).

Decrease of q_{max} (number of active Lion-ions) This parameter variation is primarily responsible for reducing the time to discharge (TTD), indicating that as q_{max} decreases, the battery ability to store and release energy diminishes.

Increase of R_0 (internal resistance) An increase in R_0 contributes to a general decrease in the output voltage of the battery during usage. This higher internal resistance leads to more significant losses within the battery and affects its overall efficiency.

Increase of D (diffusion coefficient) The variation of D mainly contributes to an increase in the equilibrium potential. As D increases, the battery tends to reach a higher equilibrium voltage after the cut-off voltage is reached.

The impact of each parameter on model performance is illustrated in Fig. 4, where each parameter effect is analyzed independently. This approach highlights the primary influence of each parameter while acknowledging that the overall impact is interconnected when all three parameters vary simultaneously.

Fig. 5 showcases the model ability to simulate the battery performance over its lifetime by manipulating the three degradation parameters. This visual representation demonstrates how changes in these parameters can effectively capture and replicate the evolving behavior of the battery as it degrades over time.

4. Cobylya optimization

The accurate estimation of degradation parameters in lithium-ion batteries is critical for understanding and managing their performance over time. These parameters are essential for characterizing how a battery behavior changes as it degrades. Importantly, these parameters are not directly measurable through conventional means. Hence, specialized methods are required to infer them.

One such method employed for this purpose is the COBYLA (Constrained Optimization BY Linear Approximations) algorithm. COBYLA is a powerful numerical optimization technique that is particularly well-suited for estimating parameters in situations where direct measurements are not possible or are prohibitively expensive. It allows us to find the values of these parameters that best match the observed behavior of a battery over time, considering the complex interplay of physical processes involved in battery degradations.

It is a derivative-free optimization algorithm designed to find the minimum of a scalar function subject to constraints. The choice of a derivative-free optimization algorithm, such as COBYLA, is driven by the non differentiability of the objective function at the maximum discharge point. Furthermore, the computational efficiency of

Fig. 4. Impact of the variation of the degradation parameters q_{Max} (a), R_0 (b), and D (c) on the model performance.

Fig. 5. Results of the calibration of the model degradation parameters at the beginning and end of the battery life show that variations in these parameters lead to a decreased time to discharge and an increased equilibrium potential. These phenomena are accurately simulated by the model.

Fig. 6. The 2-step optimization process, executed using COBYLA, initially accurately estimates the TTD but underestimates the equilibrium potential (orange dotted line). In the second step (blue dotted line), this discrepancy is corrected, ensuring better alignment with the actual battery voltage output. The parameter variations are detailed in Table 2. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

COBYLA compared to gradient-based methods is pivotal in our real-time application, particularly considering the necessity for a two-step optimization scheme, as elaborated later in this section. COBYLA suitability for non-smooth functions and its computational advantages make it well-aligned with the specific demands of our optimization process.

The scalar function to be minimized represents the discrepancy between the battery model predictions and the actual behavior of the battery over time. The objective is to minimize this discrepancy by adjusting the three degradation parameters (q_{max} , R_0 , and D) within specified bounds. COBYLA works by iteratively approximating the optimal values of the parameters while respecting any constraints placed on them. It employs a combination of linear approximations to the objective function and a trust region strategy. This allows COBYLA to explore the parameter space efficiently and converge to a solution that minimizes the discrepancy between model predictions and observed data. The optimization problem can be expressed as:

$$\min_{x \in \Omega} c(x) \tag{18}$$

where $c(x)$ represent the objective function, x is the vector containing the degradation parameters and Ω is the feasible region, representing the range of parameter values that are physically valid and meaningful within the context of the battery degradation model.

The definition of the objective function plays a crucial role in the performance of the optimization process. To evaluate the performances of the battery it is primarily necessary that the model precisely predicts the TTD, the general voltage output and also the equilibrium potential. For evaluating the general voltage output we resort to the mean squared error (MSE) between the model predictions and the measured data. To emphasize the importance of accurately estimating the TTD, we defined d_{TTD} , the horizontal distance in the curves minimum points, which reflects the lag in their times to discharge. Lastly we defined d_{eq} as the voltage difference in the last point of the measurement, which is a good estimation of the equilibrium potential.

Table 2
Variation of the parameters for the Cobyla 2 step scheme showed in Fig. 6.

Parameter	Starting Values	Step 1 Values	Step 2 Values
q_{max} [C]	12 500	11 421	11 421
R_0 [Ω]	0.09	0.102	0.102
D [mol s/C/m ³]	4.5×10^6	4.43×10^6	5.25×10^6

The initial simultaneous optimization of all parameters yielded sub-optimal results, particularly in estimating D , the diffusion coefficient, which controls the equilibrium potential. To solve this problem, a 2 step optimization scheme is adopted. The first step includes the simultaneous optimization of the three parameters all together, and the objective function is defined as:

$$c(x) = \alpha \times \text{MSE}(x) + \beta \times d_{TTD}(x) \tag{19}$$

α and β represent a weighting factor to control a trade-off between the two components. This work reached satisfactory results by using $\alpha = \beta = 1$. This first step allows to estimate in a satisfactory way especially q_{max} , which is strongly correlated with the TTD (this correlation is also discussed in Fig. 11), and R_0 . However, as it can be observed in Fig. 6, after the first step the distance in the last points is not well minimized (orange dotted line). This happened even when the third term d_{eq} is included in Eq. (19). To overcome this, a second step is performed by keeping q_{max} and R_0 fixed and setting the objective function as:

$$f(x) = d_{eq} \tag{20}$$

Fig. 6 provides a visual representation of the results obtained through the COBYLA optimization process for a specific curve. In this graphical representation the red line represents the actual voltage profile that has been recorded from BMS. This line represents the

Fig. 7. Historical run-to-failure data for battery B0005, where each set of three values indicates the optimal parameters identified for each cycle.

real-world behavior of the battery, which serves as the reference for our optimization efforts. The dotted yellow line reflects the voltage model output, simulated using the initial degradation parameters. It represents the starting point in the optimization process, meaning the model initial attempt to replicate the observed data. The orange and blue dotted lines, on the other hand, represent the model output after the completion of the COBYLA optimization, respectively after the first and final steps. As it can be observed, the second step has the effect of varying the equilibrium potential, while keeping the TTD almost unaffected. The blue line represents the model output with the final set of optimized parameters achieved through the overall optimization process. The variation of the parameters is reported in Table 2. Fig. 6 clearly shows the effectiveness of the optimization process in enhancing the model accuracy. It allows us to identify the parameters that provide a significantly improved description of the measured data. Notably, the optimization process excels in correctly estimating the TTD, which is the most crucial factor in the battery decrease of performance.

The optimization process serves a dual purpose in our framework (Fig. 1). First, it is utilized to acquire the run-to-failure history of the three critical parameters for battery B0005. This historical dataset, as depicted in Fig. 1 within the prognostic area at the center-low section, becomes a foundational resource for feeding the MLP-PF model, which will be detailed in the subsequent section. It is this historical data that is initially used to train the MLP-PF to make future predictions of the parameters. The run-to-failure behavior of the parameters is reported in Fig. 7

Secondly, the same optimization process is employed iteratively when new measurements become available from the BMS (calibration phase, in Fig. 1). At each new cycle of data, the optimization process is performed again, although it does not initiate from scratch. Instead, it leverages the optimal parameters obtained in the previous cycle as a starting point for the new optimization run. This iterative approach ensures that the parameters are continuously refined, adapting to real-time data. In essence, it facilitates a dynamic and ongoing calibration process that ensures that the model remains aligned to the battery evolving behavior.

5. Multi-layer perceptron particle filter

The physical model and the COBYLA optimization process allow to identify and continuously update the optimal degradation parameters during the calibration phase (Fig. 1). However these data are not exhaustive in estimating the RUL of the battery, since they only provide information on the current battery state of health. The RUL is defined as

Fig. 8. Architecture of the MLP neural network (Cadini et al., 2019).

the number of remaining cycles during which the battery can provide the requested power:

$$RUL_k = EOD_k - k \tag{21}$$

where EOD is the battery end of life estimated at current cycle k . To obtain a reliable prediction of the EOD for a given battery at a specific cycle, it is necessary to evaluate the physical model with the parameters related to its future performance. This involves propagating the degradation parameters into the future, accounting for real-time measurements and their variability, which can be influenced by the specific characteristics of the battery under observation.

The multi-layer perceptron particle filter methodology is here proposed to address this challenge. The particle filter (PF), a sequential Monte-Carlo algorithm (Doucet et al., 2000; Arulampalam et al., 2002), is employed to estimate the posterior probability density function of an hidden state x_k . It works by generating a set of N samples from a prior distribution, and updating it on the basis of a series of noisy measurements $z_{0:k-1}$. The underlying state-space is a hidden Markov model defined by:

$$x_k = f(x_{k-1}, \omega_{k-1}) \tag{22}$$

$$z_k = g(x_k, k) + \eta_k \tag{23}$$

in which Eq. (22) represent the process model, linking the current hidden state to the previous one, while Eq. (23) is the noisy measurement equation. ω and η are the process and measurement noises, both assumed Gaussian.

The PF works under the hypothesis that the functions $f(x_{k-1}, \omega_{k-1})$ and $g(x_k, k)$ are known. In our case, this is not true, as neither the relationship between the measurement z_k (which can represent q_{max} , R_0 or D) and x_k , nor the process model Eq. (22) are known a priori. To solve this issue, we resort to a MLP neural network (Bishop, 1995) to serve as a surrogate for the measurement equation $g(x_k, k)$. Therefore, Eq. (22) and Eq. (23) are redefined in the new problem formulation as:

$$x_k = x_{k-1} + \omega_{k-1} \tag{24}$$

$$z_k = \tilde{g}(x_k, k) + \eta_k \tag{25}$$

In this formulation x_k now represents a state vector containing the parameters of the surrogate model at time k , and $\tilde{g}(x_k, k)$ is the MLP neural network itself.

The three degradation parameters are propagated independently, by applying the methodology separately to each of them. To maintain brevity and clarity, the methodology is here presented for the propagation of q_{max} , which is the degradation parameter that influences the more the battery performance, in particular regarding the TTD, but the same exact reasoning applies to the other two parameters.

Fig. 8 shows the neural network architecture used in this work. It consists in a single input neuron (receiving the time step k), an hidden layer composed of 3 neurons and 1 output neuron (which returns the predicted value). The activation functions $h(\cdot)$ are sigmoids, while the output activation function $f(\cdot)$ is linear. This network consists of a total

Fig. 9. Qualitative example of the resampling process, in the simplified case of 10 particles. On the left graph is represented a uniform distribution, while on the right graph the cumulative density function (CDF) of the importance weights associated to each particle. In this case, the particle 3, which has an higher importance weight than particle 6, is more likely to be resampled.

of 6 weights and 4 biases, which are packed in the state-space vector x_k . The simplicity of the network is chosen to be able to capture the hidden pattern of the degradation parameter and at the same time avoid a high number of model parameters to be estimated by the PF, which can be computationally expensive.

The MLP is initially trained on the basis of the historical data of q_{max} (Fig. 7). The trained weights and biases of the network are grouped in x_0 , serving as the starting point for the algorithm. This initialization step enables the particles to explore the state space starting from plausible values, consistently enhancing the algorithm performance.

Therefore, the set of N_s particles is generated from the initialized state x_0 , on the basis of Eq. (24). The functioning of this process can be visualized in Fig. 12(a): the red line is the training, meaning the prediction of the NN using x_0 , the trained weight and biases obtained from a similar known battery. The green dotted lines represent the N_s predictions, each associated with a different particle x_k^i , reflecting the initial perturbation introduced to x_0 by ω_0 . This perturbation results in multiple predictions that collectively contribute to the algorithm exploration of the state-space.

The tuning of the hyperparameter ω_k is of crucial importance for the functioning of the algorithm. An excessively low value for ω_k would result in the particles becoming anchored to the training data, rendering them incapable of adapting to the incoming measurements. On the other hand, if ω_k is set too high, it would lead to a loss of prior information, resembling a process that is entirely random. Following the approach employed in prior work such as Sbarufatti et al. (2018), Gordon et al. (1993), this work computes the process noise ω as a value that decrease gradually over time:

$$\omega_k = \sigma_0 e^{-\frac{k}{\sigma_1}} + \sigma_2 \quad (26)$$

where $(\sigma_0 + \sigma_2)$ is the initial value, σ_1 indicates the rate of decrease and σ_2 is the asymptotic value. The concept behind this decreasing variance is to allow the algorithm to properly explores the state-space at the beginning, facilitating adaptation to the measurements. As we progress closer to the end of Life (EOL), the lower variation in the variance serves the purpose of stabilizing the algorithm behavior and predictions.

The task of the PF is to recursively estimate the posterior PDF $p(x_k|z_{0:k})$. This PDF represents, from a Bayesian perspective, the degree of belief in the hidden degradation state x_k (the MLP parameters), based on the past knowledge $z_{0:k}$ (the observations q_{max} obtained from the BMS through COBYLA optimization, described in Section 4). This estimation is achieved through the prediction-update recurrence (Gordon

Table 3
Hyperparameters used for the simulation.

Hyperparameter	Values
N_s	500
EOL [C]	8300 [C]
σ_0	5×10^{-2}
σ_1	10^2
σ_2	10^{-3}
η	10^{-2}

et al., 1993): the available observations until time $k - 1$ allow to compute a prior distribution $p(x_k|z_{0:k-1})$ using the N_s state trajectories (particles). Each particle is assigned an importance weight w_k^i :

$$w_k^i = w_{k-1}^i p(z_k|x_k^i); \quad (27)$$

$$i = 1, \dots, N_s$$

where $p(z_k|x_k^i)$ is the likelihood \mathcal{L}_k^i , which signifies the probability of obtaining the observation z_k given the state x_k . In the classical PF, \mathcal{L}_k^i is computed by considering only the last observation z_{k-1} , based on the Markov hypothesis. However, following the approach of Sbarufatti et al. (2018), this work considers the entire set of available observations $z_{0:k}$ to compute \mathcal{L}_k^i , which can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_k^i = p(z_{0:k}|x_k^i) = ((2\pi)^{k+1} |\Sigma_\eta|)^{-0.5} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (z_{0:k} - \bar{g}(x_k^i, 0 : k))^T \Sigma_\eta^{-1} (z_{0:k} - \bar{g}(x_k^i, 0 : k)) \right\} \quad (28)$$

where Σ_η is the diagonal covariance matrix.

Finally, the degeneracy problem (Arulampalam et al., 2002) is addressed by using the sample importance resampling (SIR) algorithm (Kantas et al., 2009, 2015): the SIR algorithm helps to prevent each particle but one from assuming nearly zero importance weights (degeneracy). This is achieved by normalizing the weights as follows:

$$\hat{w}_k^i = \frac{w_k^i}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_s} w_k^j} \quad (29)$$

Then, the particles x_k^i are resampled based on the normalized importance weights: a visual representation of the resampling process can be observed in Fig. 9. Particles with higher normalized weights, thereby representing predictive degradation trajectories closer to the actual one, are more likely to be resampled, while particles with low weights are likely to be discarded.

This approach ensures adaptability to the real trend of the measurements and enables computation of the posterior PDF at each future time instant, as shown in Fig. 10(a): the red dots represent the available observations, while the blue dot the future trend (not known to the algorithm). Each green line corresponds to a particle, thus representing one of the N_s MLP network predictions of q_{max} .

6. Remaining useful life estimation

To predict the battery RUL as defined in Eq. (21), we must establish a criterion for its EOL. Typically, a battery is considered to reach EOL when its capacity declines below 80% of the initial capacity, which, in our scenario (with a constant discharge current), is closely linked to the time to discharge. To optimize the utilization of the available dataset, the authors opted to set the threshold at 2400 s, corresponding to a remaining capacity of approximately 70%. Furthermore, as highlighted in Nascimento et al. (2021) and illustrated in Fig. 11, there exists a nearly perfect correlation between the TTD and the degradation parameter q_{max} . This significant correlation enables us to directly link the EOL threshold to the q_{max} parameter. As a result, the task of estimating the RUL becomes much simpler, eliminating the need to evaluate the physical model to obtain the TTD. The EOL threshold is hence defined as the cycle at which the q_{max} parameter drops below the value of 8300 C. With this definition we can compute EOL_k^i for

Fig. 10. Left graph: shows the propagation of q_{max} parameters through MLP networks. Each green line represents a particle, with the green area covering the 95th percentile. The red dot represents current observations, and blue circles denote future observations unknown to the algorithm. Right graph: posterior probability density function (PDF) for the parameter at future cycle 143, as indicated by the grey dotted line in the left graph. The blue circle represents the true value, and the red star denotes the mean of the PDF. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Depiction of the correlation between the time to discharge and the optimal q_{max} parameter for battery B0005.

each MLP prediction i for current cycle k , from which it is possible to build the posterior PDF $p(\text{EOL}_k | z_{1:k})$ and consequently its statistics.

The performances are evaluated using the α - λ plot and the β metric (Lall et al., 2010), the cumulative relative accuracy (CRA) (Saxena et al., 2008) and the confidence interval coverage (CIC) (Jules et al., 2023).

The α - λ plot compares the accuracy of the prediction with respect to the ground truth remaining useful life (RUL^{GT}). λ represents the normalized time and is defined as $\lambda = (k/T_{fail})$, where k is the time step and T_{fail} is the time step associated to the end of life. Hence, $\lambda = 1$ corresponds to the end of life of the battery. The α -bounds, calculated at each time step k as $\text{RUL} \pm \alpha$, represent a goal region for the prediction to be considered as successful. In this work we use $\alpha = 0.2$. The β metric is computed starting from the α - λ plot, and assesses the quality of the RUL prediction by measuring the probability density that falls within an acceptable region around the true RUL. It is calculated as:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{T_{fail}} \sum_{k=0}^{T_{fail}} \int_{\text{RUL}_k - \alpha}^{\text{RUL}_k + \alpha} \text{PDF}(\widehat{\text{RUL}}) d\text{RUL} \quad (30)$$

This metric evaluates how much of the predicted RUL probability distribution falls within the acceptable bounds (α). In other words, it measures how confident the model is in its prediction based on how

much of the probability density lies within a predefined acceptable range. It allows to discriminate between predictions with different levels of associated uncertainty: a high β metric indicates a superior RUL prediction.

The CRA quantifies the overall accuracy of the predicted RUL with respect to the ground truth, evaluated at each time step. It is defined as:

$$\text{CRA} = \frac{1}{T_{fail}} \sum_{k=0}^{T_{fail}} \left(1 - \left| \frac{\text{RUL}_k^{\text{GT}} - \text{RUL}_k^{\text{pred}}}{\text{RUL}_k^{\text{GT}}} \right| \right) \quad (31)$$

A perfect prediction has a value of 1. This metric emphasizes errors closer to the failure of the battery, highlighting the importance of making good predictions close to the EOL. Essentially, it gives a sense of how accurate the predictions are over the entire degradation period, focusing on errors as the system approaches failure. This metric is particularly useful because it emphasizes accuracy as the system approaches the end of life, when the cost of prediction errors is highest.

The CIC measures how often the ground truth RUL falls within the predicted confidence intervals throughout the degradation process. It is given by:

$$\text{CIC} = \frac{1}{T_{fail}} \sum_{k=0}^{T_{fail}} \mathbb{1}_{\text{RUL}^{\text{GT}} \in \widehat{\text{CI}}_k} \quad (32)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{\text{RUL}_k^{\text{GT}} \in \widehat{\text{CI}}_k}$ is the indicator function, returning 1 when the ground truth RUL lies within the predicted confidence interval and 0 otherwise. If the prediction interval includes the RUL^{GT} at each time step, the CIC is 1, while is 0 if the ground truth RUL is always outside the confidence interval. The CIC evaluates the quality of the confidence interval provided by the model, assessing not just point predictions but also the uncertainty surrounding those predictions. High CIC indicates that the confidence intervals provided by the model are reliable, covering the true RUL most of the time.

In Fig. 12, four different instances during a simulation are illustrated. The hyperparameters used for this test can be found in Table 3. The test use the parameters obtained from battery B0007 of the NASA dataset as training, while predicting the performance of battery B0005. The raw voltage data are obtained from commercially available Li-ion 18650 sized rechargeable batteries, in controlled laboratory conditions at 24 °C and subjected to a constant load of 2 A. In the figure, the blue dots represent future q_{max} observations, which are unknown to

(a) Predictions at first cycle. The red line indicates the initial training.

(b) Evolution of the predictions after 50 cycles.

(c) Evolution of the predictions after 80 cycles.

(d) Evolution of the predictions after 120 cycles.

Fig. 12. Four instances of the propagation of q_{\max} during a single simulation. The green lines represent the N_s particles, meaning possible degradation trajectories of the parameter. The blue dots are the future observations, while the red dots are the available ones (from zero to the current cycle k , vertical red dotted line). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the algorithm, while the red dots represent the observations available at the current time k . Initially, the particles explore the state space starting from the training. As soon as new measurements obtained from the Cobyta optimization process become available, the algorithm adapts itself and modifies its predictions accordingly. It is important to note that the peaks observed, which are related to the capacity recovery phenomenon (Eddahech et al., 2013), add complexity to accurately estimate the battery behavior. These peaks can have a variation ranging from 3% to over 10% cycle over cycle. Comparing Figs. 12(b) and 12(d), we can appreciate the effect of the decreasing variance, as described in Eq. (26). The dispersion of the trajectories is more significant in the initial steps of the algorithm, gradually converging toward the end, as the algorithm can rely on more information about the current battery. The algorithm strong adaptability to incoming measurements is evident when observing the trajectories behavior. Initially, they overestimate the EOL, following the training. Then, the EOL is underestimated, aligning with the real behavior of the battery between cycle 48 and the significant capacity phenomena around cycle 90: during this phase, the battery degradation seems more pronounced, with a steeper slope. In Fig. 12(c), the algorithm ability to adapt is clear. Without the peak, the battery would likely reach the EOL threshold earlier. Even in this scenario, the algorithm captures the underlying dynamics, adjusts the particle importance weights accordingly, and ultimately converges to an accurate EOL estimation. The history of the RUL prediction for this simulation is depicted in Fig. 13, while the evaluation metrics are provided in Table 4. These metrics are calculated over both the entire lifecycle and the final quarter. Notably, both the CRA and CIC metrics increase during the last quarter compared to the overall lifecycle. Specifically, a CIC of 1.00 indicates that, in this final quarter, the prediction bounds consistently contain RUL^{GT} at each prediction step. Conversely, the β metric shows a slight decline, which can be attributed to the constancy of prediction bounds during the last quarter. Meanwhile, the alpha bound narrows as it nears failure time, thus lowering the β metric value.

Fig. 13. Variation of the predicted RUL over time during the simulation.

Table 4
RUL evaluation metrics.

Metric	Overall Life	Last quarter
β	0.338	0.296
CRA	0.740	0.833
CIC	0.626	1.000

Once the mean value of the estimated posterior PDF $p(EOL_k | z_{1:k})$, denoted \hat{EOL} , is identified, it becomes possible to compute the PDFs for the other two degradation parameters, R_0 and D , at $k = \hat{EOL}$. These posterior PDFs for the three degradation parameters are then used to sample their values, following a classic Monte-Carlo approach. This allows for the evaluation of the battery performance at the predicted cycle $= k$. In Fig. 14, the results of a Monte-Carlo simulation are presented. The true battery output voltage at the cycle $k = 143$ is the red dotted line, while each grey line represents a battery simulation with the triples of parameters sampled from the three PDFs. The blue line represents the average value, and the green line represents the average ± 3 times the standard deviation. This simulation refers to the time

Fig. 14. Results of the Monte Carlo simulation of battery performance at the EOL, using parameters estimated at cycle $k = 120$ for future cycle $k = 143$, identified as the battery EOL.

instant $k = 125$, meaning the one depicted in Fig. 12(d). It is worth noting that the ground truth is almost entirely inside the green lines, and that the TTD and the equilibrium potential are correctly estimated. This evaluation of the battery performance is useful for estimating the probability that the battery can still provide the required power. It also helps in planning corrective measures in advance, such as a repair or a replacement, based on the simulation results.

7. Conclusion

This paper presents a novel, hybrid grey-box approach to lithium-ion battery prognostics, combining physical modeling with a multi-layer perceptron particle filter to deliver real-time, adaptable predictions of battery health and RUL, using raw data from the battery management system. By employing Modelica for detailed physical modeling and integrating it through Python functional mock-up interface, this approach streamlines model implementation and optimization, achieving strong alignment with actual battery performance in validation tests. This fusion of physical and data-driven modeling not only improves model explainability but also enhances flexibility in adapting to battery-specific degradation patterns, making it highly practical for real-world applications. While the framework demonstrates promising accuracy and adaptability, future work could focus on demonstrating its applicability across various battery chemistries and operating conditions, as well as refining parameter independence assumptions to enhance prediction robustness. These ongoing advancements hold potential for further enhancing predictive accuracy, supporting efficient battery management, and advancing the understanding of lithium-ion battery degradation in practical prognostic and health management applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Francesco Cancelliere: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation. **Sylvain Girard:** Supervision, Writing – review. **Jean-Marc Bourinet:** Supervision, Writing – review. **Matteo Broggi:** Supervision, Writing – review.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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